

INCREASING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

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It is impossible to imagine life and development without women. They are considered to be the leading forces of the society, skillful and capable trainers and intelligent educators. Today, it is difficult to solve almost every problem of the society, even the task of building a great country in the future, without the participation of women. In terms of building a great country in the future, we rely primarily on the young generation. Raising a child begins with proper family upbringing. What kind of people our sons and daughters in the family grow up to be depends above all on our women. As the first President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, said, "Those who unite the family and our society, bring blessings to it, illuminate our homes with the light of love, elegance, and goodness are actually our honorable mothers, our sisters."

Even at the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, great attention is paid to the issue of women. All conditions are being created for their active participation in various areas of our society. The reforms carried out in the country in terms of protecting the rights and legal interests of women, increasing their economic, social and political activity, maintaining their health, providing vocational training and employment, wide involvement in entrepreneurship, social support for needy women, ensuring gender equality A number of practical works are being carried out in order to systematically continue, as well as to consistently implement the goals of the United Nations Global Agenda for Sustainable Development. In particular, Uzbekistan became one of the first among the CIS countries to join the UN Convention "On the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women", the International Labor Organization's Conventions "On Protection of Motherhood", and "On Discrimination in the Field of Work and Training". These documents are part of the complex of regulatory and legal documents aimed at protecting the interests of women and strengthening their position in the family and in the society as a whole.

On the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, special attention is being paid to increasing the social and political activity of women, protecting their health, supporting their initiatives, and creating decent working and living conditions for them. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 2021 No. 736 "On the introduction of additional measures and amendments to certain

legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the adoption of additional measures to guarantee the rights of women in severe social situations", 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5325 of February "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and strengthening the family institution", March 5, 2021 "Further improvement of the system of supporting women and ensuring their active participation in community life" on measures" Resolution No. PQ-5020, "On additional measures for the rehabilitation of women victims of violence" Presidential Resolutions No. PQ-5116, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 14, 2021 "Women support state trust fund activities No. 210, dated August 9, 2021, No. 507, dated September 17, 2021, No. 507, dated August 9, 2021, "Representatives of socially needy families, orphans or dependents of their parents "On measures to financially support the higher education of deprived female students" No. 585, December 6, 2021 "Provision of housing for women in need of housing and homeless women who have fallen into difficult living conditions in the city of Tashkent As a result of the adoption of decisions No. 737 on measures to improve the living conditions of citizens, the socio-political activity of women has increased, conditions have been created for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, to ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected, special attention was paid to comprehensive support of motherhood and childhood, as well as strengthening of the family institution.

A number of preferences and opportunities have been given to women in our society on the basis of the laws adopted in order to increase the socio-political activity of women in state administration and to support the part of them who are in a difficult social situation. In particular, as a result of the establishment of the State Fund for the Support of Women and Girls;

- to pay the down payment for housing to women in a difficult social situation, including persons with disabilities, women raising children with disabilities, low-income women, raising children in single-parent families, and women in need of improving housing conditions;
- assistance in financing activities related to all-round support of women, health care, development of women's sports, improvement of work and study conditions;
- allocating resource funds to commercial banks for all-round support of women's business initiatives;

- it was established to support the financing of activities related to the creation of necessary conditions for women to acquire knowledge and skills in occupations that are in high demand in the labor market.

In addition, the Internal Affairs authorities started issuing protection warrants to women who suffered from harassment and (or) violence. The following are grounds for issuing a protection order:

- appeal of a victim of oppression and violence;
- messages of individuals or legal entities, including messages spread through mass media and (or) social networks;
- direct identification of cases of oppression or violence or attempts to commit them by employees of authorized bodies and organizations;
- materials received from state bodies and other organizations.

In particular, by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's decision PQ-5116, a model center for rehabilitation and adaptation of women was established. According to the decision:

- The republican center for rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of violence and suicide prevention was completed;
- The Republican Center for Rehabilitation and Adaptation of Women and its regional departments were established under the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support.

Also, by the decision, 29 republican, regional and inter-district exemplary centers (centers) were created for the rehabilitation and adjustment of women. One of the main tasks of the centers is to anonymously provide urgent medical, psychological, social, educational, legal and other assistance to women who have suffered from oppression and violence, committed suicide or are prone to suicide. The following are placed in the centers:

- women affected by violence and their minor children;
- women who have committed suicide or are prone to suicide.

According to the Decree of the President No. PF-6155, within the framework of the State Program for the implementation of the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health Strengthening", the procedure for training some women at the expense of hokims and higher educational institutions was introduced.

On the basis of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 285, women who have fallen into a difficult social situation, women with disabilities, low-income mothers, who are raising their children in single-parent families and need to improve housing conditions (based on the recommendation of housing commissions established in the municipalities, affordable housing the initial contribution amount was exempted from paying through a mortgage loan.

Also, by the decision of the government, the regulation on the procedure of mutual electronic cooperation of state bodies and organizations within the framework of the single interactive national platform "Aziz-ayol.uz" was approved. The main task of the single interactive national platform "Aziz-ayol.uz" is:

- quick collection and real-time analysis of information related to women from ministries and agencies is ensured;
- Vocational training of women included in the "Women's Register", ensuring their employment, and attracting them to entrepreneurship will be supported;
- uniform facilities will be created for women to apply for the protection of their rights.

Women from needy families are recommended to participate in the competition for admission to higher education institutions based on the state grant based on the following criteria:

- women from low-income families;
- girls in need of social protection who are brought up in single-parent families, that is, their father or mother or both of them have died;
- women in need of social protection whose spouse has died and who are raising their minor child alone;
- women in needy families with disabled children;
- Daughters of single women raising 2 or more children, living separately from their relatives;
- women in needy families with one or both of their parents having disabilities of group I or II. In order to receive a recommendation, it was established to apply electronically to district (city) neighborhood and family support departments.

Also, women included in the "Women's Book" and who want to engage in entrepreneurship have been granted loans of up to 150 times the BHM for a period of up to 6 months with a grace period of no more than 3 years.

According to the legislation, the badge "Honorable Woman" was established, with this badge:

- showed activity and initiative in society and state life;
- made a significant contribution to the formation and strengthening of the family's well-being, motherhood and childhood protection with his effective work;
- women who are doing exemplary work in bringing up a healthy and mature generation, educating them in the spirit of patriotism and independence, improving the moral and moral environment in the localities and widely promoting our national values are awarded.

Law No. 562 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" was adopted. As a result, equal participation of women and men in the competition for positions in the public service, including leadership positions, was ensured.

The personnel services of the state bodies are obliged to provide the selection commissions not only with the information about the education and professional training of the persons participating in the competition, but also with the information about the ratio of the number of women and men working in the relevant positions of the public service. Also, it is prohibited to dismiss women at the initiative of the employer due to the fact that they have reached the retirement age.

Starting from the academic year 2022/2023, the contract fees of all women studying at master's degrees in state higher education institutions have been covered, and at least 200 billion soums have been allocated annually for this, and women with 5 years of work experience in their specialty will be admitted to study on the basis of a recommendation letter. On the basis of the Presidential Decree "On measures to support women's education in higher, secondary special and professional educational institutions" from the 2022/2023 academic year in all private, foreign and state higher, secondary special and professional educational institutions in the republic full-time, part-time and A new system of allocating funds from the State budget to banks was introduced in order to finance education loans under preferential conditions for women's education in the form

of evening education on the basis of a fee-contract. According to the decision: educational loans are allocated at the rate of 14 percent; the main part of the education loan is repaid for 7 years, starting from the seventh month after the end of the official period of study of the student; family members with a permanent source of income and other third parties are allowed to participate as joint borrowers in issuing and repaying the education loan; Pledges and guarantees are not required for educational loans allocated to women of families included in the "Unified Register of Social Protection". Interest rates on education loans are set to be amortized by the Education Loan Financing Fund.

The above-mentioned practical actions and reforms are fully compatible with the principles of an enlightened society and a welfare state. The socio-political activity of intelligent women leads to the solution of many social issues in state administration.

As a result of the study of the mechanisms that serve to increase the influence and opportunities of women in public administration and increase their political activity in the new Uzbekistan, the following conclusions were reached:

Hundreds of scientific projects and studies are being conducted worldwide to investigate the impact of women's political activism on society and politics. It can be seen in practice that these researches benefit not only women, but also the whole society. Among them: a) the formation of women political leaders caused a change in the nature of politics and international relations, that is, the attitude to previously "not worthy of attention" issues, such as gender inequality, reproductive health, changed in a positive direction; b) it was emphasized that it can be achieved by improving the quality of health care, social protection and education to support the vulnerable sections of society; c) the wider involvement of women in political activity has not reduced the number of men in politics, but has made it possible to create mutual support and cooperation of both sexes in building a society with more fair and equal opportunities for all; g) The large number of women in the parliament creates the basis for the adoption of laws that serve their interests. In short, women's political activism has changed the political landscape. In the period of political changes and reforms in Uzbekistan, it is important to support the women's strata and ensure their social and political activity. In particular, within the framework of requirements for recognition and sufficient influence in the world community, indicators in achieving women's rights and gender equality are a leading factor. In particular, reforms aimed at ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all

women in the field of sustainable development are consistent with the tasks of implementing international programs. In order to operate on an equal and broad scale in the world arena, ensuring the fulfillment of international requirements and communicating in mutual harmony remains one of the priority directions of the policy of the state of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Қонуни, 09.12.2021 йилдаги ЎРҚ-736-сон - <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/5766205>
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони, 02.02.2018 йилдаги ПФ-5325-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/3546742>
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг қарори, 14.04.2021 йилдаги 210-сон-<https://lex.uz/docs/5370790>
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг қарори, 04.01.2020 йилдаги 3-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/4676892>
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг қарори, 19.05.2021 йилдаги ПҚ-5116-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/5426644>
6. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг қарори, 02.04.2018 йилдаги 257-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/3607779>
7. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Қонуни, 02.09.2019 йилдаги ЎРҚ-562-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/4494849>
8. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг қарори, 07.03.2019 йилдаги ПҚ-4235-сон - <https://lex.uz/docs/4230944>
9. Маткаримова Г.А. Аёл ҳуқуқлари ва гнелдер тенглик. Конституцияда инсон ҳуқуқлари ҳимояси. Илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. – Т.: ТДЮИ, 2012. –Б.31.
10. Inter - Parliamentary Union (IPU). Global data on national parliaments. Global and regional averages of women in national parliaments // <https://data.ipu.org/women-averages>.
11. IPU Parline. Global data on national parliaments. Monthly ranking of women in national parliaments. Ranking as of 1st October 2021 // <https://data.ipu.org/women-ranking?month=10&year=2021>

